

mixture was then cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was neutralised by the gradual addition of glacial acetic acid. The resulting colourless solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (1.3 g, 65%), m.p. 250° (Found : S, 25.2. C₉N₅S₂H₉ requires : S, 25.4%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 410–3 100br (NH), 2 420 (SH), 1 600, 1 560 and 1 415 cm⁻¹.

3-[4-(4'-Oxothiazolidinyl-2-imino)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-a]triazole (4) : A mixture of 3 (2.51 g, 10 mmol), monochloroacetic acid (2 g, 20 mmol) and anhydrous NaOAc (0.5 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The excess of solvent was then evaporated and the resulting slurry was poured into crushed ice. The resulting light yellow solid was filtered off, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (1.46 g, 50%), m.p. 190° (Found : S, 19.0. C₁₃N₅S₂O₂H₉ requires : S, 19.3%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 210br (NH), 2 955 (CH₂), 1 710 and 1 730 (carbonyls in different environment), 1 600, 1 570 and 1 500 cm⁻¹.

3-[4-(5-Benzylidene-4-oxothiazolidenyl)imino]phenyl-6-benzylidene-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-a]triazole (5; Ar=C₆H₅) : A mixture of 4 (1.1 g, 3 mmol), benzaldehyde (0.7 g, 6 mmol) and anhydrous NaOAc (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2.5 h. After cooling, the deep yellow solution was poured into crushed ice and the resulting yellow solid was dried and recrystallised from acetic acid (0.65 g, 60%), m.p. 205° (Found : S, 12.4. C₂₇N₅S₂O₂H₁₇ requires : S, 12.6%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 200br (NH), 1 725 and 1 740 (carbonyls in different environment), 1 620, 1 590, 1 510 and 1 430 cm⁻¹.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE THIAZOLIDINONES (5)

Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	Analysis S% † Found/ (Calcd.)
p-Anisyl	140	66	1 710, 1 730	11.0 (11.20)
p-Chlorophenyl	128	60	1 720, 1 740	11.01 (11.10)
p-Bromophenyl	146	55	1 715, 1 730	8.86 (9.14)
p-Nitrophenyl	178	50	1 700, 1 720	9.61 (9.73)

The physical and analytical data of the other diarylidenes are given in Table 1.

References

- V. K. CHADHA, C. S. PANDA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 910; T. B. ACHARY, C. S. PANDA and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1065; K. S. L. SRIVASTAVA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1968, 37, 315; J. SAWLEWICZ, K. WISTEROWICZ and H. CIRAH, *Acta Pol. Pharm.*, 1976, 33, 681; S. K. MALLICK, A. R. MARTIN and R. G. LINGARAJ,

J. Med. Chem., 1971, 14, 528; K. C. JOSHI and J. S. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 139; A. R. KITTLESON, H. L. YOWELL, C. A. COHEN, R. S. HAWLEY and P. V. SMITH, Br. Pat. 716 533/1954 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, 49, 12543).

- M. SAHU, B. K. GARNAIK and R. K. BEHERA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, 26, 779; J. SAHU, S. S. MEHER, S. NAIK and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 71; B. K. GARNAIK and R. K. BEHERA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 456.
- M. CLEASON, P. VAN and H. VENDERHAAGHA, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1954, 6, 127.

A New Flavonol Glycoside from Guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L. Taub)

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IN a previous paper¹, we reported the presence of myricetin-7-glucoside-3-glycoside, kaempferol-7-glucoside-3-glycoside, texasin-7-O-glucoside and daidzein-7-O-glucoside in guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L. Taub), an important legume crop. In the present communication, a new flavonol tetraglycoside has been reported.

Samples (1 kg) of dried, powdered seeds/leaves were refluxed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°, 4 dm³) for 4 h. It was followed by two extractions with 80% aqueous methanol (3.5 dm³ each), under reflux for 4 h each time. The combined methanolic extracts were filtered and concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure.

Both one-dimensional and two-dimensional paper chromatography were employed using Whatman no. 1 paper for qualitative purpose and Whatman no. 3 paper for preparative work. The solvent systems used were: butan-1-ol–acetic acid–water (4 : 1 : 5, v/v/v) and aqueous acetic acid (2.2%, v/v).

The specific detecting reagents used were (i) FeCl₃–K₃Fe(CN)₆: phenolic compounds, (ii) ethanolic 1% (w/w) AlCl₃: flavonols, (iii) ethanolic 1% (w/w) FeCl₃: di-OH-phenolics, (iv) sodium metaperiodate benzidine reagent²: phenolic glycosides, and (v) aniline hydrogen phthalate: reducing sugars.

Acid hydrolysis of flavonol glycoside (Found : C, 50.03; H, 5.3. C₃₉H₅₀O₂₆ requires : C, 50.1; H, 5.35%) was carried out in 95% ethanol–2M HCl (1 : 1) at 100° for 1 h. Aglycones were detected under uv light whereas sugars were identified by spraying aniline hydrogen phthalate reagent³. Partial hydrolysis was carried out in 1M HCl for

30 min at 100° and this method of Harborne⁷ was employed for the quantitative estimation of aglycones and sugars.

Acid hydrolysis⁸ of flavonol glycoside gave myricetin, L-rhamnose and D-glucose. The behaviour of peaks at 258, 268 and 357 nm in its uv spectra, in the presence of NaOAc, NaOMe and AlCl₃ was in agreement with those of myricetin-3-O-glucoside-7-O-rhamnoside or myricetin-7-O-glucoside-3-O-rhamnoside; thus indicating the absence of free phenolic group at C-3 and C-7. Flavonol glycoside was treated with acetic anhydride and pyridine at room temperature to give the acetylated product. The ¹H nmr (90 MHz; CCl₄) spectrum of acetylated derivative showed signals at δ 1.9–2.25 (48H, s, 1 × acetate-CH₃), 0.92–1.35 (6H, unresolved-d, 2 × rhamnose-CH₃), 3.45 (2H, s, rhamnose/glucose-C-1-H), at 3.65–3.97 (2H, diffused-q, rhamnose-C-5-H), 4.1–4.4 and 4.9–5.45 (20H, m, primary and secondary H of glucose/rhamnose), doublet and multiplet at 6.7 (1H, J 3 Hz, Ar-6-H), 7.03 (1H, J 3 Hz, Ar-8-H) and 7.4–7.8 (2H, Ar-2', 6'-H). The glycosylation of 7-hydroxyl group was supported by downfield shift⁹ in pmr spectra (indicated by signals at δ 6.70 (d, 6-H) and 7.03 (d, 8-H) to shift downfield). Moreover, in ¹H nmr (90 MHz, CDCl₃) spectra of silylated flavonolglycoside, the sugar region showed signals at δ 1.15 (6H, d, J 6.5 Hz, 2 × rhamnose-CH₃), 4.5–5.1 (2H, m, rhamnose/glucose-C-1-H), 2.9–4.2 (20H, m, primary and secondary-H of glucose/rhamnose), and doublets at 6.27, 6.75, 7.1 and 7.92 (1H each, J 9.0 Hz each, Ar-2', 6', 6, 8-H).

Mass spectral fragments¹⁰ m/z 450, 362 (terminal glucose, rhamnose), 378, 289 (internal glucose, rhamnose), 590 ((aglycone + H) – 15) and 740, 651 (1→2, interglycosidic linkage) and ¹H nmr spectra (TMS ether)⁸ of flavonol glycoside and its acetyl derivative confirmed that parent glucoside contained two rhamnose and two glucose units; m/z (rel intensity %) 740 (0.5), 651 (0.5), 590 (0.6), 502 (0.8), 487 (4.1), 450 (3.3), 430 (8.2), 415 (6.5), 378 (1.6), 363 (4.1), 362 (3.3), 361 (9.0), 289 (6.5), 273 (2.5), 217 (23.8), 204 (19.7), 191 (4.9), 169 (4.9), 157 (6.5), 147 (22.9), 129 (18.0), 117 (12.3), 103 (19.7), 85 (4.9), 75 (31.1), 74 (13.1) and 73 (100). Therefore, the structure of flavonol tetraglycoside might be either 3-O-(2-rhamnosylglucosyl)-7-O-β-glucosylrhamnosylmyricetin or 3-O-(2-glucosylrhamnosyl)-7-O-β-rhamnosylglucosylmyricetin.

The position of the glucosidic and 3-O-(2-rhamnosylglucosyl) or glucosidic and 3-O-(2-glucosylrhamnosyl) was determined by enzymatic hydrolysis⁸ of flavonol tetraglycoside with β-glucosidase, which supported the latter, i.e. 3-O-(2-glucosylrhamnosyl)-7-O-β-(2-rhamnosylglucosyl)myricetin; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 725, 1 045 (OCOCH₃), 1 600, 1 430, 1 370 (C=C), 1 760, 1 135, 1 080 (C=CCO) and 2 920 cm⁻¹ (CH); λ_{max} (methanol) 257, 359; (+NaOCH₃) 271, 400; (+AlCl₃) 276, 435; (+AlCl₃ - HCl) 270, 406; (+CH₃COONa) 260, 382; and (+CH₃COONa +

H₂BO₃) 259, 376 nm; λ_{max} (hydrolysed; methanol) 257, 374; (+NaOCH₃) 274, 452; (+AlCl₃) 256, 310 (sh), 372 (sh), 452; (+AlCl₃ - HCl) 257, 423; and (+CH₃COONa) 258, 420 nm.

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References

1. G. P. KAUSHAL and I. S. BHATIA, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1982, 33, 461.
2. G. M. BARTON, R. S. EVANS and J. A. F. GARDNER, *Nature (London)*, 1952, 170, 249.
3. T. H. GAGE, C. D. DOUGLASS and S. H. WENDER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 1582.
4. K. FINK and R. M. FINK, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1949, 70, 654.
5. J. A. CIFONELLI and F. SMITH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1132.
6. J. B. HARBORNE, "Phytochemical Methods", Chapman and Hall, London, 1973, p. 216.
7. J. B. HARBORNE, *Phytochemistry*, 1965, 4, 107.
8. T. J. MABRY, R. K. MAKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of the Flavonoids", Springer, Berlin, 1970.
9. J. B. HARBORNE and T. J. MABRY, "The Flavonoids", Chapman and Hall, London, 1975.
10. H. SCHELS, H. D. ZINSMEISTER and K. PFLÜGER, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, 16, 1019.

Chemical Constituents of the Orchid *Dendrobium farmerii*: Further Evidence for the Revised Structure of Dengibsin

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WE reported earlier^{1-4,6-28} a number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These compounds represent several structural types, such as bibenzyls¹⁻³, phenanthrenes⁴⁻¹¹ (both monomeric and dimeric), phenanthropyrans¹² and pyrones¹³, 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes¹⁴⁻¹⁶ (both monomeric and dimeric), 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrans¹⁷⁻²³ and pyrones^{13,17-19,23}, simple aromatic compounds²⁴, triterpenoids^{25,26} and steroids^{27,28}. As part of this general programme of research we have chemically investigated yet another new Indian orchid *Dendrobium farmerii* which has afforded the fluorenone derivative dengibsin (2a), two coumarin derivatives ayapin and aesculatin dimethyl ether and p-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid. These compounds were characterised